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Vitamin C and the Cold

To the Editor:

Your Nov. 30 editorial "Preventing the Common Cold"¹ grossly misrepresents my book, "Vitamin C and the Common Cold."

The major misrepresentation is in the following sentences: "A scientific fact can only be established by controlled experiments, and it is likely that Professor Pauling's espousal of this notion will spur physicians to carry out the needed tests. He asserts that previous work in this field failed to show positive results because the doses of vitamin C employed were too small."

In fact, I discuss in the book the reports of nineteen studies, some of which involved well-controlled experiments. Of these nineteen studies, sixteen gave positive results. An example is the 1942 investigation by Cowan, Diehl and Baker, described by Dr. Frederick J. Stare as "a very careful study."

These three physicians reported 15 per cent smaller incidence of colds in the students who received 200 milligrams a day of vitamin C than in those who received a placebo. They stated, "The actual difference between the two groups during the year of the study amounts to one-third of a cold per person. Statistical analysis of the data reveals that a difference as large as this would arise only three or four times in a hundred through chance alone. One may therefore consider this as probably a significant difference, and vitamin C supplements to the diet may therefore be judged to give a slight advantage in reducing the number of colds experienced."

A very careful double-blind study of the effect of 1,000 milligrams of vitamin C per day was reported in 1961 by the Swiss physician G. Ritzel. He reported a reduction of 61 per cent in the number of days of illness from upper respiratory infections and a reduction of 65 per cent in the incidence of individual symptoms in the vitamin C group as compared with the placebo group.

In the book I discuss also three careful studies that gave negative results. In two of these studies the patients were given ascorbic acid for three days only, beginning after the cold had been contracted. In the third study, carried out by Drs. Walker, Bynoe and Tyrrell in 1967, the subjects received three grams of ascorbic acid per day for nine days, or a placebo. They were inoculated with cold viruses on the third day. No protective effect of ascorbic acid was observed under these conditions.

I did not state in my book that previous work in this field failed to show positive results because the doses of vitamin C employed were too small. I stated that the evidence summarized in the book shows that even small amounts of, ascorbic acid, taken regularly, have some value in providing protection against the common cold, and that a number of scientists and physicians have reported that the common cold can be almost completely controlled by use of still larger amounts.

LINUS PAULING

Stanford, Calif., Dec. 2, 1970

¹ Editorial (1970 Nov 30) Preventing the common cold. New York Times
<https://www.nytimes.com/1970/11/30/archives/preventing-the-common-cold.html>
<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1970/11/30/76800339.html?pageNumber=40>